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Evaluation Of Teachers' Readiness To Integrate Artificial Intelligence (AI) For Teaching Biology In Senior Secondary Schools Of Potiskum, Yobe State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates teachers' readiness to integrate Artificial Intelligence into the teaching of Biology in senior secondary schools of Potiskum educational zone, Yobe state. The study adopted descriptive survey research design and was guided by one research question and one null hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study comprises of all the 109 Biology teachers in Potiskum educational zone. A questionnaire on teachers' readiness (BTRIAIT) was used for data collection. Data for the research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used for the null hypothesis. The finding of the study revealed that Biology teachers are ready to integrate Artificial Intelligence in teaching Biology. There was a very strong positive correlation between Biology teachers readiness, benefits and availability of facilities $r = .995$ $n = 109$. Based on this, it was recommended that stakeholders in education and Yobe state government should ensure the enforcement and regular supervision on the use of Artificial Intelligence in teaching Biology in secondary schools. Teachers should be familiar with the ethics of AI application and integration in teaching practices and there should be routine teacher professional development on the use of AI in teaching.

Keywords: teachers' readiness, Artificial Intelligence, Biology

INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education is developing new methods, strategies and solution for teaching and learning, including administrative and security situations of academic community (Xu, 2024). Aina, Gbenga-Epeinu, Olapfinbiyi, Ogidan, and Ayedun (2023), defined Artificial Intelligence as a computer system with an innovative technical framework that is having the ability to carry out activities that usually need human intellect. AI is a machine programmed human intelligence simulation that is capable of thinking and learning like human (Cooper 2023). The effectiveness of AI application in education is strongly attached to the knowledge, skills and readiness of teachers/educators to apply AI in their teaching. Teachers who have the knowledge and are ready to utilize AI, might soon replace those who do

not have that quality, (Xu, 2020). Al-Darayseh (2021), observed that, AI is now regarded as a fundamental pillar in Science Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education, it plays a significant role in aiding teachers in their role as facilitators and assessors of learning. The use of AI tools and application in secondary school science and biology in particular, has the potential to fundamentally transform the methods of teaching and learning, thereby enhancing accessibility engagement and educational effectiveness (Soma, 2018). Nikolopoulou, Gialamas, Lavidas and Komis, (2021), opined that, exploring teacher's intention and readiness in utilizing and implementing AI in teaching is important, since their acceptance and disposition could be a pointer to their interest in using AI, and how to impact their teaching practices.

Education sector seek to incorporate innovative ways to enhance teaching and learning through modern methods by teachers, it is important to explore the extent of teacher's awareness, readiness and integration of these valuable tools and applications into education realm, Johnson and Adebayo, (2022). Sok and Heng, (2023), carried out a study on the multifaceted potential of AI tools and applications for educational improvement, they reveals that, there is need for the importance of understanding the pedagogical implication of AI and also the necessity of cultivating awareness among educational professionals to harness it benefits. In the opinion of Dakakni and Safa (2023), teachers need to know as a matter of urgency how to integrate tools with AI and thus, guide their students appropriately. In a study conducted by Celik (2022), he states that, teachers should be able to understand, justify and evaluate the AI tools to be used. Similarly, Farrelly and Baker (2023), Hasanein and Sobaih (2023), point out the need for teacher professional development training on AI and how it works. Huang, Saleh and Liu, (2021) says, understanding the problems and or challenges teachers might encounter when using AI, will help people to be better prepared and improve the future utilization and application of AI in education. In the opinion of Nguyen, Ngo, Hong, Dang and Nguyen (2023), the integration of AI into teaching and learning, need to be mindful of privacy and ethics. AI system is capable of making a mistake or providing incorrect data. If such a thing happened, it's difficult to hold anyone accountable.

For Nigeria's education sector to be at par with global standard, Federal Government has been urged to incorporate the use and application of AI in the education sector. AI as one of the global emerging technologies, if properly included in the school curriculum, it will adequately make for an easy learning experience for the learners, and make teaching by teachers easy and dynamic. The problem of insurgency and kidnapping ravaging northern Nigerians communities (Yobe inclusive), science education require the type of teaching that enables resources and application of AI tools to be appropriately invested. Zhao and Watterson (2021) opined that, before the effect of global pandemic and specifically insurgency in North Eastern Nigeria, Biology learning was carried out directly using real biological objects. As a result of these factors, real objects used in biology learning must be replaced with learning media such as photos, videos, animations etc. To achieve the aforementioned goals, Kotsis, (2024) opined that, teachers need to be ready to accept the changes which come with it, possess the knowledge and be ready to integrate AI tools and application if they need to flow with the global trend and contribute to the success of teaching and enhance a dynamic learning process. Therefore, this study aims to examine the teachers' readiness to integrate AI in teaching Biology in senior secondary schools in Potiskum education zone, Yobe state, Nigeria. The study seek to answer: what is the Biology teachers' readiness to integrate Artificial Intelligence in teaching Biology? The null hypothesis is: there is no significant relationship between Biology teachers' readiness to use AI I teaching and the benefits of using AI in teaching.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research designs. Descriptive research design involves the collection of data from member population in order to determine the status of the population with regards to one or more variable (Adeyemi, 2008). The study was conducted in Yobe State and precisely Potiskum educational zone. The target population of the study were all (109) biology teachers drawn from Potiskum educational zone Yobe state constituted the population of the study. The instruments used for the study were questionnaire titled: Biology Teachers Readiness to Integrate AI in Teaching (BTRIAIT), designed by the researcher for biology teachers. The data generated for the study was analyzed using Statistical

Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26. The research question was answered using descriptive statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation (SD). While, the research hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance, using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC).

RESULTS

Research Question *What is the Biology teachers' readiness to integrate Artificial Intelligence in their teaching?*

Table 1 Descriptive statistics on the readiness of Biology Teachers to Integrate Artificial Intelligence in their Teaching

S/no	Item	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I understand the basic concepts of AI relevant to teaching Biology	2.61	4.92	Agree
2	I am confident in my ability to use AI tools for teaching Biology	2.96	15.06	Agree
3	I can easily learn new AI tools that are introduced for teaching Biology purposes.	2.77	9.18	Agree
4	I feel prepared to tackle minor issues with AI technology in the classroom teaching Biology.	2.91	12.61	Agree
5	I can evaluate the effectiveness of AI tools in enhancing Biology learning.	2.64	4.57	Agree
6	I can comfortably explain the benefits and limitations of AI Biology students.	3.03	14.93	Agree
7	I am comfortably ready to prepare and present my Biology lesson using AI tools.	3.06	15.99	Agree
8	I can integrate AI teaching tools with traditional teaching methods.	2.71	8.62	Agree
9	I am familiar with some AI tools for teaching Biology.	2.74	13.67	Agree
10	I have sufficient knowledge to use AI tools in teaching Biology.	2.40	8.02	Agree
11	I feel confident to use AI tool in teaching Biology.	2.81	10.59	Agree
12	I am open to learning new educational AI tools.	2.69	7.09	Agree
13	I find it easy dealing with Biology AI tools I teaching	2.39	8.77	Disagree
14	I am familiar with ethics of AI applications	2.93	13.02	Agree
	Grand Mean	2.76		Agree

Results presented in table 1 above contain respondents' perception on the readiness of Biology teachers to integrate artificial intelligence in their teaching. The result showed that respondents were in agreement with all the 13 of the 14 question items raised, but however, disagreed on the extent which students access computer and internet for their learning. With 32 of the respondents (Mean=2.39) saying this is only available to a low extent. However, the grand mean of 2.76 recorded shows that respondents were all in agreement with the items generally.

Hypothesis 1 There is no significant relationship between teachers' readiness to use AI in teaching and benefits of using AI in teaching.

Variable	Correlation coefficient (r)	P value	N
Readiness to use AI * Benefits of Using AI	0.995	<0.05	109

The result of the correlation analysis of association between teachers' readiness to use AI in teaching and the benefits of using AI in teaching revealed that there was a very strong positive correlation between the two variables which is also highly significant ($p < 0.995$). Thus, we reject the hypothesis that there is no significant association between teachers' readiness to use AI in teaching and the benefits of using AI in teaching

DISCUSSIONS

The finding of the study as related to research question one (1) Readiness of Biology teachers to integrate AI in their teaching, in table 1 revealed that the respondent were in agreement with the question items raised. This is in agreement with the finding of Harry (2023), where he observed with keen interest that, Artificial Intelligence has the potential to revolutionize the way we learn and teach, making it more personalized, engaging and efficient. On the contrary, Alnasib (2023), in his study reported an average readiness to integrate AI into their teaching with mean = 3.40. While Al-Darayseh (2023) observed there has been growing interest in Artificial Intelligence and how to apply it effectively in the educational process. Ayanwale et'al (2022), found out that confidence in teaching with AI predicts intention to teach AI while AI relevance strongly predicts readiness to teach with AI. Specifically, Hassoun et'al (2020), carried out a research on general Biology and reported, AI technologies will allow us not only to collect, connect and analyze data at unprecedented scale, but also to build comprehensive predictive model that span various sub discipline. On the contrary, Mercedes and Lucy (2023), reported readiness of AI integration in geoscience were they are used to support either knowledge construction in skill development, were learning achievement, argumentation skills, learning experience and teaching the impact of AI application.

Findings related to hypothesis 1 there is no significant relationship between Biology teachers readiness to use AI in teaching and the benefits of using AI in table 4, revealed that, there was a very strong positive correlation between the two variables which is also highly significant ($p < 0.995$). Therefore we reject the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between teachers' readiness to use AI in teaching and the benefits of using AI in teaching. This finding support the opinion of Xu (2024) where he observed that, the evolvement of AI technology is having the potential to transform and impact education through accepting AI by teachers. As AI in education holds the promise to revolutionize our teaching methodology and learning pattern he added.

The findings of the study are as follows:

That, Biology teachers are ready to integrate Artificial Intelligence into their teaching, with few disagreed to the extent by which students' access internet and computers in their respective schools. That, great benefits are achieved using AI in the teaching of Biology. That, there is a very strong positive correlation between Biology teacher readiness to use AI in teaching, and the benefits of using AI in teaching Biology.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the finding of the study, it was concluded that the level of Biology teachers' readiness to teach using AI is to a very high extent, Biology teachers have observed a great benefit while using AI tools and application in their teaching. That, a very strong positive correlation exists between Biology teachers' readiness, and benefits of using AI in teaching.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the study, following recommendation are made

1. It is obvious that, the effectiveness of AI application in education is strongly attached to the knowledge, skills and readiness of teachers/educators to apply AI in their teaching. Therefore, stakeholders of education and Yobe state government should ensure the enforcement and regular supervision on the use of AI in teaching.
2. Teachers should be familiar with the ethics of AI application and integration in teaching practices.
3. There should be routine teacher professional development on the use of AI in teaching.

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